

EVOLUTIONARY HISTORY OF HUMANS IN EURASIA USING ANCIENT DNA DATA

¹Sharibjonova Sayyorakhon Abdurashidovna, ²Mamasolieva Marjona Jamoliddinovna,

³Urmanov Xurshid Nurjanovich

^{1,2} Students of the Department of History of the KSPI named after
Mukimi Kokand city, Uzbekistan

³ Lecturer at the Department of Biology, KSPI named after
Mukimi, Kokand, Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *Advances in ancient genomics provide unprecedented insight into modern human history. Recent progress in identifying prehistoric populations in Eurasia based on ancient DNA studies from the Upper Pleistocene to the Holocene is reviewed here. There were many ancient populations in the Upper Pleistocene of Eurasia, some with no significant lineage related to modern populations, some related to East Asians, and some contributing to Native Americans. By the Holocene, the genetic composition throughout East Asia had changed significantly, with several significant migrations. Three of them are directed south: an increase in the number of ancestors associated with the northern part of East Asia in the southern part of East Asia; the movement of ancestors associated with East Asia to Southeast Asia, mixing with ancestors from Main Asia; and the movement of ancestors from southern East Asia to the islands of Southeast Asia and the Southwest Pacific as a result of Austronesian expansion. We expect additional ancient DNA to expand our understanding of genetic history in Eurasia.*

Keywords: *DNA, Genetics, Eurasia, history of the peoples of Eurasia.*

About the history of peoples, about conquerors since the time of Alexander the Great, about tribes and peoples, ancestors and modern inhabitants of Eurasia. Many believe that the history of a people can be studied separately. But in fact, for example, without the history of the Turks it is impossible to understand the history of the Russians. When almost all hypotheses have already been formed, it may be that some data about other peoples, contradict a theory that we were already almost sure of. The formation of nations and peoples took place even under capitalism. The peoples consisted of tribes whose history went back centuries. The best thing, - be critical of theories that some kind of people already existed in antiquity, although now historical figures are often attributed to some kind of people, for example, Jesus Christ is attributed to the Jews, to a nation that was formed over the previous 200 years. The writing of the ancient tribes dates back to 5500 years BC. It is impossible to understand and explain the history of peoples only at some point in time, or in some limited area of space, for example, in Armenia. History is rewritten to please the rulers, so ideas about justice have always changed, as well as the names of cities and entire states changed. Historical evidence is coins, souvenirs, finds of archaeological research, chronicles, maps, correspondence of maps, petroglyphs - images on stones, pyramids, literary works. The results of the analysis of similarities and differences in modern languages, DNA statistics in modern peoples, and DNA of the remains of ancient burials are also historical evidence. Archaeological finds can be objects brought from other countries, and it is important to distinguish utensils, tools from souvenirs. There are also cases of "cooperation" of scientists who made mutual assumptions that were beneficial for their countries. Languages of communication

and writing are valuable material for historical research, but linguistic and tribal communities do not always coincide. For example, the Hungarians, whose linguistic culture is the Xiongnu, representing only about 2% of the entire Hungarian nation. Genetic studies are becoming more and more important materials in confirming or refuting historical hypotheses as data on X and Y chromosomes in different peoples are accumulated and systematized. In each person, each cell contains an identical set of 23 pairs of chromosomes. The pair of chromosomes responsible for the sex of a person can be set XY (male) or XX (female). Both male and female chromosomes are examined. Chromosomes are structures within cells that contain a person's genes. Genes are contained in chromosomes, which are found in the cell nucleus. One chromosome contains hundreds to thousands of genes. Each normal human cell contains 23 pairs of chromosomes, that is, a total of 46 chromosomes. The male hereditary material does not change by itself - the changes were caused by the female chromosomes. The systematization of female genetics is very complicated - women from different tribes were taken as wives. Namely, genetic studies allow us to clarify, confirm or refute certain hypotheses that are formed by researchers of history. In deep history, modern types of chromosomes are almost never found. And if we see the oldest haplogroups among modern people, then this indicates the antiquity of their kind. Scientists determine the time of possible mutation of prehistoric chromosomes, the sequence of their origin. Not everything is so simple - if the history of gene mutations from 140-150 thousand years is restored along the line of the progenitor of mankind, Eve, then the progenitor, Adam, has only 80-120 thousand years. In genetic studies, both types of Y - chromosomes and X - chromosomes are important. Analysis of Y -chromosomes already allows us to draw conclusions about the origin of people along the paternal lines. The types of human haplogroups are determined, starting with A, B, - all subsequent haplogroups of men were formed by mutations - changes in genes. Probably, the mutation could have occurred in more than one person, since there is a "tree of haplogroups". In total, according to various sources, from 25 to 40 thousand genes have been described in humans, although there is evidence of a much larger number of human genes. A gene is a logically isolated section of genetic material that is repeated from cell to cell (helices based on deoxyribonucleic acid - DNA). Only about 1.5% of a person's genetic material is associated with genes that are transmitted according to Mendel's laws, the rest of the space also carries some important information that has not yet been studied. It is possible that unknown spaces in the hereditary material serve to transmit acquired information, data from ancestors. DNA genealogy believes that commonality develops from one person who has a given mutation. And therefore, all calculations in DNA - genealogy are of a model nature. Mankind has been developing for millions, billions of years, and all the time mankind has been developing from small communities. And the Earth was saved from humanity by floods and fires. After nuclear wars, ice ages arose that lasted for millennia. The last ice age probably began about 14,000 years ago. And the civilizations of the Scythians and Sumerians took the countdown in the annals is about 5500 BC. Haplogroups A, B were found only in Africa, with model calculations, about 80-100 thousand years ago. With a mutation 40-50 thousand years ago, haplogroup C was formed, which is generally attributed to Mongolia, Central and East Asia. A mutation in the B group led to the creation of the F group . At this time, peoples with haplogroups G , IJK , H arise - these are immigrants from Africa. In the next 100 thousand years, the origin of man can be imagined -

B -> DE

DE -> D (Tibetans) E (Arabs) (60,000 years old)

ST -> C (Mongols) T (60,000 years)
IJK -> I (Slavs) J (Semites) K (Celts)(20 thousand years)
NOP->NOP
NO -> N (Xiongnu) O (Chinese)
P -> R
R -> R 1 (Eurasia) R 2 (Americans) (20 thousand years)
R - R 1 a (Scythians) R 1 b (Sumerians)

Before the ice age, the probable origin of DE is Tibet, the expansion of groups D and E - towards Africa. The origin of the Arabs is associated with E. Haplogroup D 1 is found among the Tibetans (as well as among the inhabitants of mainland East Asia, where the "parent" haplogroup D is extremely rare), haplogroup D 2 - among various population groups of the Japanese archipelago, haplogroup D 3 - among the inhabitants of Tibet , Tajikistan and in other mountainous regions of the south of Central Asia. Migrants with haplogroups D , could come both to Scythia and to Sumeria. The main haplogroups of the Sumerians were - R 1 b , T , D. During the Ice Age, the general direction of tribal migration was from north to south, to Africa, Mongolia and India. Eastern and western directions of migration existed at all times, the northern direction was associated with the retreat of the glacier in central Europe, which began about 13,000 years ago, since that time, the process of migration of tribes in the direction from Assyria to the north began. The Celtic-Iberian expansion forced the carriers of haplogroups I 1, I 2, whose main location was on the Mediterranean coast, to migrate towards Scandinavia, Finland, Russia (I 1 northern Slavs), the carriers of haplogroup I 2 (southern Slavs) went westward to the territory of modern Russia, part of the tribes remained in the mountains of Montenegro. The language of the Montenegrin Slavs is the basis of the Russian language. In modern Russia statistics (haplogroups) I 1 - about 7%, I 2 - about 15%. The South Slavic language, the speakers of which are great - ancestors - (I 2), became the basis of the Russian language.

Distribution of haplogroup I (I 1, I 2) in Europe by nationality

Bosnian Croats - 73% Dargins - 58% Sardinians - 42.3%

Bosniaks - 42.0% Norwegians - 40.3% Swedes - 40.0%

Danes - 38.7 Slovenes - 38.2% Serbs - 29.2%

Russian Cossacks - 22.7% Ukrainians - 21.9% Russians - 22.0%

Moksha - 19.3%

The age of the male haplogroup R is about 20 thousand years (the end of the Ice Age). These haplogroups are found in Azerbaijan, in Kazakhstan. The warming that took place 8,000 - 12,000 years ago caused the expansion of the peoples of Africa to the north, towards Spain, and the peoples of the Russian Plain migrated to the north, from Siberia - to the northwest (N). Sumerian differences and Scythian lines in that R 1 b on the Russian Plain are immigrants from the west, and R 1 a in the west are immigrants from the east.

The peoples of haplogroups C, N , O - formed in Mongolia, in southern Siberia, in China. Tribes Q - Siberian - Americans, Mayan people, O 3 a - Han (Chinese), O 1 - Japanese, O 2 - Koreans, N - South Siberian tribes. Japan has O 1, O 2, O 3 - but most O 1.

History, since the time of Alexander the Great, is the history of conquest. Alexander the Great made his campaigns against Scythia (329 - 327 BC). Crimea was the center of the Scythian kingdom, with its capital near modern Simferopol. Sacred places of the Scythians are near Yalta, Melitopol. The Scythians lived along the banks of rivers and seas; different Scythians had both a

sedentary and a nomadic lifestyle. There were no "forest" Scythians - and the Scythians began to hide in the forests after the invasions of foreigners. The people of the Scythian kingdom were characterized by the main haplogroup R 1 a . And now they have not yet found the ancient remains of a Scythian with a haplogroup not R 1 a . The Scythian kingdom was united after the conquest of Asia and India by Alexander the Great. Both R 1 a and R 1 b were formed from the same people. But R 1 b is the western haplogroup, the haplogroup of the pharaohs, and R 1a is the haplogroup of the Scythians, Aryans. Area is area, space, and Sum area is a union of spaces, rivers. Ar is proud. The Sumerians are the ancient ancestors of people with haplogroups R 1 b 1, T. The chronicles of the campaigns of the world king Alexander the Great in Central Asia and Afghanistan do not testify to big battles. A campaign in Central Asia (329-327 BC) is a struggle with the Scythian tribes between the Amu - Darya and Syr Darya. The offensive of the troops of Alexander the Great to the north was limited by the Syrdarya River (Yak Sart). The conquests of Alexander the Great did not have the goal of destroying countries - however, he subjugated the rulers of the peoples. In Tajikistan, Alexander the Great founded the city of Alexandria Eskhata (Alexandria Extreme), now it is the city of Khujand (Khujand). The city of Kandahar in Afghanistan was also founded by Alexander the Great, the city was also called Alexandria. The fighting of Alexander the Great was not conducted on the territory of modern Kyrgyzstan and above the Syr Darya - they were fought in Central Asia in Uzbekistan, Tajikistan and Afghanistan. In Afghanistan (Bactria), in 327 BC. e., Alexander married Roxana (Rohan), the daughter of the local nobleman Oksiart, they had a son. The great king and commander, Alexander the Great did not lose a single battle, conquered India, and died before he was 33 years old. The Scythian kingdom with its center in the Crimea lasted until the second half of the 3rd century BC. AD and was destroyed by the Khazars. The army of the Khazars were Bashkirs and Huns (Argyns, Arguns). Argyns G 1 and Xiongnu N together now represent the Hungarians. Kazakhs have Argyn statistics. Archaeological research, excavations show that the Scythians were tall people. In battle, the Scythians held the reins of the horse in their teeth, and they held weapons, spears, swords, shields, with both hands. The Scythians were fair-haired. Burials of the Scythian princesses frozen in the permafrost were discovered in the Northern Altai already in our time. Archaeological research distinguishes some tribes of the Scythians with malocclusion of teeth - this is probably evidence that in these tribes the Scythians held the reins of horses in their teeth. Probably, the Scythians were forced to master martial arts because of the constant danger from foreign raids. When the conquerors attacked the Scythians, the Scythians (Saks, Russaks), left to the north, to the forests, and to the east, to Mongolia. The attacks of the Goths and the Khazars came from the western direction. There is no data on the residence of the Kyrgyz during the conquest of Central Asia by Alexander the Great (3rd century BC) - but there is evidence of the partisan war of the Scythians in the Syr Darya - that is, these data are evidence of the Scythians living in this territory. One can trace the sequence of the existence of states on the territory of Russia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan.

1. Scythian kingdom. The capital of the kingdom was in the Crimea. The Scythians lived on the shores of the seas, rivers from the Black Sea to the Pacific Ocean, along the Amur River, inhabited the banks of the Amu-Darya, Syr-Darya rivers, the shores of Lake Issyk-Kul.

2. The Scythian kingdom was united after the conquest of Crimea, Asia and India by Alexander the Great.

3. After the conquest of the Scythians by the Khazars in the 3rd century AD, the state of the Hephthalites - the Huns and Bashkirs - was formed.

The Scythians went north and east. Part of the Scythians remained on their lands (Drevlyans). The composition of the Khazars is very complex, these are the ancestors of the Bashkirs (R 1 b 1), Semites (J 1, J 2), G 2. Unlike G 1, the G 2 tribes were not warlike, and were educated. The presence of the haplogroup R 1 b among the modern peoples of Eurasia may not only indicate the belonging of their ancestors to the conquerors of Scythia. These haplotypes are now common in Western Europe, among the Germans (60%), the French, and the Irish R 1 b - about 90%. For different tribes of the Bashkirs, the values of R 1 b vary. Namely, for the Perm and Baimak Bashkirs, the R 1 b 1 statistics are 84% and 81%, respectively. The Burzyan, West Orenburg and Saratov-Samara Bashkirs have 33, 23 and 18%, respectively. The Eastern Orenburg and Abzelil Bashkirs have 9% and 7%, respectively. Haplogroup R 1 b 1 was not found at all among the Sterlibashevsky Bashkirs of the Cis-Urals (Lobov's research). The Bashkir tribes Berish and Tabyan are among the Kazakh tribes. Modern Kazakhs have about 6% R 1 b and about 12% G 1 (Argyns). It is absolutely fair to attribute J to the Semites, and I to the Slavs, although some researchers attribute R 1 a and even N to the Slavs. The Kyrgyz have up to 70% R 1 a, these are not Slavs. Both Semites and Slavs are descended from the IJKL people. But the Jews treat the Semites in the same way as the Greeks - Cypriots, as well as the Azerbaijanis and Armenians; - in their communities J - about 40%. And Russians are only a quarter (22%) Slavs. Some peoples of the North Caucasus are Semites - Chechens and Ingush, 60-90% J. Haplogroups do not determine nationalities, but statistics of haplogroups in different peoples are important for research. Some peoples Caucasians have more lines of Semites than Jews. The Scandinavians have up to 40% of the lines of the northern Slavs, and even more than the Serbs. There is historical evidence that in Sweden 300 years ago the language was understandable for modern Russians, when writing words in Latin. Among the Jews - Sephardim, the Spanish line of Jews, mixed with the Western European migration flow, which was sent to Spain, corresponds to the haplogroup R 1 b 1 (Africa -> Spain). Ashkenazi - Slavic - German line of Jews, which was of eastern origin, corresponds to the Slavic - Aryans - I, R 1 a. The data of the founder of DNA - genealogy, A.A. Klyosov, These data calculate the time of the appearance of the Jews on the tree R 1 a 1 - 54 generations ago, 650s of our era (7th century). it also indicates the time of penetration of R 1 a 1 - to the Jews, as 1350 years ago. According to many sources, the haplogroup R 1 a 1 is found in Jews - Ashkenazi 7-10%, the same occurrence of haplogroup E in Jews - Sephardim, they also, with approximately the same frequency, occur - R 1 b 1, however R 1 b 1 arose among the Jews much earlier, among the Jews, the time of the appearance of haplogroups, -

J - 17500 years J 1 - 15500 years K, T - 8500 years

E 1 b 1 b - 6800 years J 2 - 6000 years R 1 b - 5000 years

I 1 - 4100 years G 2 - 4000 years G 1 - 3600 years

I 2 - 1400 years R 1 a 1 - 1350 years (7th century) Q - 675 years

R 2 - 650 years G 2 c - 575 years I 21 b - 500 years

statistics G 2 among the Jews of Israel - about 10%, among the Palestinians - 9%. Nationality does not correspond to the haplogroup. Nationality is the self-identification of a person and his identification society. There are no "Jewish" or "Armenian" haplogroups, and our concepts of Semites and Slavs can only be conditional. We can assume that the carrier R 1 a is a Slav, but we still cannot attribute R 1 a to the Slavs as the original haplogroup. In the same way, the Turks have Chinese haplogroups O, but we will not be able to attribute the Chinese to the Turks. The emergence of communities Semites and Slavs - a common event, this follows from the origin of

IJKL -\u003e I , J , K , L and I -\u003e I 1, I 2; J - > J 1, J 2. Many historians associate the formation of related tribes J 2 with Crete, J 1 - Qatar, Yemen, where (E + J) - up to 90%. J 2 is among the tribes of Kazakh dulats, Ingush (89%), Chechens (57%), Dagestan peoples. J 1 also has a Caucasus distribution. For Armenians, Georgians, Turks, Azerbaijanis - statistics (J 1 + J 2) about 30-50%. During the invasion of Nazi Germany, the North Caucasian peoples of ancient Semitic origin, I. Stalin moved to Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan.

Origin of the Swedes

In Swedes, R 1 a 1 occurs in about 24%. R 1 a 1 a 1, R 1 a 1 a 2 - Scandinavians. The table below shows how the Indo-European migration of the Scythians (R 1 a 1) determined the formation of the peoples of Europe.

Frequency of haplogroup R 1 a 1, %

Russians (north) 34 Russians (center) 47 Russians (south) 55

Belarusians 50 Ukrainians 54 Poles 56

Slovaks 47 Czechs 38 Slovenians 37

Croats 34 Serbs 16 Bulgarians 15

Lithuanians 34 Latvians 39 Finns 6-9

Swedes 24 Germans 8 Germans (Bavarians) 15

British (east) 9 Romanians 20 Tatars - about 30% R 1 a 1

Pashtuns (Afghans) - 35% Kyrgyz - 60% Kazakhs - 30%

Iranians - 35%

historical the origin of the haplogroup R 1 b 1 in Russia is the Huns (Bashkirs), in whom this group has significant statistics, and immigrants from Western Europe. In total, in Russia now - about 5% of the Russian population have the haplogroup R 1 b 1. The haplogroups N , O are of South Siberian and Chinese origin. N 1 c - probable origin - Altai, Far East, - about 3500 years ago, the same founders of Russia as the Slavs (I 2) and their northern branch of line I - (I 1). Haplogroup O carriers are Naimans, among the Naimans 3/4 O, 1/4 G 1 (Argyins). Tatars have statistics N 2, N 3. Tribes R 1 a 1 - can be called the founders of the Russian people, and tribes N 1 c , I 2, I 1 and other tribes - the founders of the Russian people, whose modern language is now based on the language of the Slavic tribes (I 2). In Mongolia, the tribes of the Oirats, Katons and other tribes have the statistics of the haplogroup R 1 a 1. The statistics of the Mongols are also group C, which the Kazakh tribes have, in particular, C3c The movement vector of the Indo-Europeans - Scythians (R 1 a 1) to the north , was the progenitors of the tribes Russians, Ukrainians, Poles. In Russians, the occurrence of haplogroup R 1 a 1 is somewhat less than 50%, while in Ukrainians and Poles it is slightly more than 50%. The rulers of the Golden Horde (Ak - Horde), - lines C, C3 and R 1 a 1. Genghisides have Mongolian haplogroups C. There is no exact data on the haplogroups of Genghis Khan and Timur. Probably Genghis Khan had haplogroup C3, and Timur R 1 a 1. Timur Tamerlane died in 1405 and was buried in a mausoleum near Samarkand. Gerasimov was instructed to study the remains of Timur, from the grave, opened in 1941. According to many sources, Gerasimov was instructed to make the portrait of Timur as Mongolian as possible. In the Golden Horde (Ak-Orda), in the Timurid dynasty (until 1450), power could only belong to the descendants of Genghis Khan. It is possible that Abulkhairkhan 1, who became the head of the Kazakh Khanate in 1428, has the same haplogroup - R 1 a 1.

Conclusion. From 6-8 millennia BC , on the territory of modern states - Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, the Scythians lived, presumably, until the 3rd-5th centuries of our era. Buddha - sak,

(zak), hypothetical haplogroup - R 1 a 1. Images of the Buddha have been preserved in Afghanistan.

The Celtic-Iberian expansion (R 1 b 1) is associated with the retreat of the glacier from central Europe. At the same time, migrations of peoples with genetics (I) - to the east, I 1 - in a northerly direction, I 2 - in a southerly direction arose. Origin of peoples (R 1 b 1) - Africa.

The origin of the Russians is from Russians, Russians. The Scythians, who went further west, towards Prussia, are Prussians, Prussians.

The origin of the word Bashkirs - (bash, bass) - chief, (kir, kyr) - input, offensive. The frequency of occurrence of the R 1 b 1 group among Russians, Kazakhs, Uzbeks is about 4%, these are ethnic Bashkirs and descendants of Western settlers.

The Scythians spoke a language close to modern Turkic languages. However, Russian people speak a language much closer to the language of the South Slavs - (I 2), whose homeland is the Balkans. The Northern Slavs (I 1) borrowed the Romance languages, as did the common descendants of the R 1 a 1 lines living in Germany, Norway, Scandinavia, the descendants of the Scythians, Mongols, Persians, Arabs, Chinese - including Tatars, Turks, Buryats, Bashkirs, Turks , speak languages close to the language of the Scythians.

The peoples of the ancient Slavs, Europeans (I) and ancient Jews (J), Scythians and Sumerians formed about 20 000 years ago, during the beginning of warming. Slavs and Semites descended from the same people. Probable formation J 1 - Qatar, Yemen, and J 2 - Crete. I - Mediterranean, Sardinia. The expansion of R 1 b 1 to the north caused the migration of I 1 , I 2 in an easterly direction, I 1 - northeast, I 2 - south. The frequency of occurrence of I 2 a - in Russia is more than 10%. General statistics I - about 20%. The South Russian Cossacks have slightly more than 20%. In Jews, the frequency of group J is about 30-40% In Ashkenazi Jews, there is a haplogroup R 1 a 1 (about 10%), among Sephardic Jews there is a Western European haplogroup R 1 b 1 (less than 10%). Ashkenazi Jews include Slavic (Belarusian, Polish) Jews origin - I 2. The origin of Russians, Ukrainians, Belarusians, - about half - is due to the haplogroup R 1 a 1 a 7, about 50%, which is of Scythian origin, from R 1 a 1. Only 20% of Russians are ancient Slavs, others are probable the progenitors of Russians, Ukrainians, Belarusians are the peoples of southern Siberia, the Mongolian component of C among Russians, Tatars is less than 1%, about half of the Russian people are of Indo-European origin R 1 a 1, among the Tatars - in various samples, 30 - 35%. The Tatars also have lines N 2, N 2, R 1 b 1. The language of the ancient Slavs was predominant in the formation of the Russian language. The language of the Scythians passed to the Turks and Tatars, the Russians and the peoples of Eastern Europe speak the language of the southern Slavs I 2. 2. In the 5.6 centuries - the territory of modern Russia, Kyrgyzstan and Kazakhstan, was part of the kingdom of the Hephthalites. Expansion from the west is associated with the lines R 1 b 1, G , J 1, J 2 which is present among modern Bashkirs (R 1 b 1), Armenians, Georgians, peoples of the North Caucasus (J 1, J 2, G 1), Kazakhs (G 1) Hungarians (G 1). Despite the fact that the Hungarians of the N line - about 2%, they speak the Finno-Ugric language, their main ancestors are the Argyns. Lines R 1 a 1 among the Indo-Europeans (Scythians, Saks). Indo-Europeans R 1 a 1, unlike the nomads, were engaged in crafts, agriculture, stall keeping of animals. The Mongolian lines among the Kazakhs are R 1 a 1, C 3 c (nomads), the Chinese lines are N (Russians, Tatars), O (Naimans, Uighurs, Uzbeks). The Naimans have about a quarter of the G 1 statistics (Argyns). The Turkic ethnos was formed on the basis of the Indo-European statistics R 1 a 1, the statistics of the Huns, Hephthalites, Arabs, Persians. Northern Russians (N 3) and

Turks (N 2, N 3, O, C) are of Chinese, South Siberian, Mongolian origin. The haplogroups R 1 b 1, G , J among the Turks were formed from the tribes that came from the west and conquered the Scythian kingdom. Chingizid lines, statistics of haplogroup C, find these haplogroups of her among modern Mongols, Kazakhs - up to 60%. Among Russians, Tatars, this group has statistics of less than 1%. Significant C statistics in Kalmyks, Yakuts. The Golden Horde existed from 1224 - 1395, and was part of the Mongol Empire from the beginning of the formation of the Golden Horde, to 1266. In 1266, under Khan Mengu-Timur, it gained complete independence, retaining only a formal dependence on the imperial center of Mongolia. The Mongol conquerors, Genghis Khan, Timur Tamerlane, were of Indo-European origin, R 1 a 1.

The Golden Horde was defeated by Timur, and the capitals Sarai - Batu and Sarai - Berke were destroyed by Timur 10 years before his death, in 1395. 7 Empire of Timur. Timur's war with the Golden Horde, with Tokhtamysh, with the Samanids, with the Khazars, Bulgars, with the countries of the Caucasus. The collapse of the Golden Horde. After the collapse - the formation of khanates that joined Russia. After the death of Timur, in 1428, Abulkhair Khan from the Shaybanid dynasty took power in Eastern Desht-i-Kypchak, which marked the beginning of Kazakh statehood. The state of Timur existed until 1450. The probable haplogroup of Abulkhairkhan is R 1 a 1, all the rulers of the Ord are descendants of Genghis Khan, the most probable haplogroup of Genghis Khan is R 1 a 1. Searches for Mongolian lines C in Russia give almost nothing - their statistics among Russians, Tatars - less than 1%. Abulkhair Khan II , who lived in the 18th century, was a descendant of the Genghisides. The probable genetic origin of the Romanovs is R 1 b 1 (immigrants from Western Europe). Probable haplogroup Hitler - R 1 b 1, according to the DNA of his relatives. The probable origin of Stalin is G 2 a 1. By order of Stalin, data on the remains of Yaroslav, Tamerlane and other rulers were classified, the remains of Yaroslav were seized in Kiev in 1939, and Tamerlane - in the Samarkand region, in 1940. The origin of Stalin is classified (probably -G2) _ Lenin. Genetic statistics do not reflect any advantages or disadvantages of people, they only testify to the history of peoples, confirm or refute certain hypotheses. Haplotypes and haplogroups do not provide a basis for determining nationality, but can be used to determine kinship. Haplotypes for 111 markers provide an opportunity for detailed genetic studies.

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